

UX issues found in Software Startups

The purpose of this research project is to investigate how User eXperience (UX) work has been carried out in software startups. We refer to software startups as emerging companies whose main objective is to develop innovative software-intensive products, constantly searching for a repeatable and scalable business model. For more information about startups, see <https://startups.co.uk/analysis/what-is-a-startup/>

In our early work we identified some UX-related issues that we are aiming to find out how widely these issues are faced by startups. We kindly invite you to this survey that is open to professionals working in software startups, including software engineers, testers, UX designers, project managers, product managers, software architects, among others. There are no restrictions on the size of the startup.

This survey should take fifteen to twenty (15-20) minutes of your time approximately to complete. The questions of this survey were organized into 5 sections contained contain questions about: the participant's background in Section 1, startup characteristics in Section 2, UX work carried out at startup in Section 3, UX issues found in startups in Section 4, and our final considerations in Section 5.

Your participation in this research study is voluntary. You may choose not to participate. If you decide to participate in this research survey, you may withdraw at any time. If you decide not to participate in this study or if you withdraw from participating at any time, you will not be penalized.

Your answers will be anonymous, and we will take all reasonable steps to make sure that they remain confidential. The data gathered in this study will be stored securely until all the publications from the survey are published. It will not be possible to identify you in any outputs from this research. The results of this study will be used for scholarly purposes only and may be shared with the researchers of this research project.

This survey is conducted by researchers at Federal University of São Carlos (Luciana Zaina, Joelma Choma), Open University of UK (Helen Sharp, Leonor Barroca), and Federal University of Pará (Cleudson de Souza, Letícia Machado). If you have any questions about the research study, please contact at jchoma@ufscar.br or lzaina@ufscar.br

Thank you for your participation!

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Clicking on the "agree" button below indicates that:

- you have read the above information
- you voluntarily agree to participate
- you are at least 18 years of age

If you do not wish to participate in the research study, please decline participation by clicking on the "disagree" button.

1. Please select your choice below.

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Agree
- Disagree

Company type information

2. Do you work in a startup that develops software-intensive products or provide software development services?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes *Pular para a pergunta 3*
- No *Pular para a pergunta 50*

Section 1: Demographic information

The following questions refer to the background information of the participant.

3. What is your age? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 18-24 years old
- 25-34 years old
- 35-44 years old
- 45-54 years old
- 55-64 years old
- 65 years or older

4. What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Secondary School
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- Ph.D. or higher
- Outro: _____

5. Which professional profiles best reflect your current job in the startup you work for? *

Select all that apply.

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Founder/ Owner
- Chief Executive Officer (CEO)
- Chief Technology Officer (CTO)
- Business Analyst/ Requirement Engineer
- Project Lead/ Project Manager
- Product Manager
- Test Manager/ Tester
- Software Architect
- Software Developer
- Data Engineer/ Data Scientist
- Scrum Master
- Product Designer
- Design Lead
- UX Researcher
- UX Strategist
- Outro: _____

6. How many years of practical experience do you have in your area of expertise? *

7. How long have you been working for the startup? *

Section 2: Startup characteristics

To answer the questions, consider the startup you are working for.

8. Where is the startup you work for located? (city, state, and country) *

9. When was the startup founded? Inform the year (e.g., 2021). *

10. Briefly describe the product(s)/service(s) developed in the startup. *

11. How many employees does the startup have? *

12. How many people work primarily in software development? *

13. How many customers/users does the startup have? *

14. What is the classification of the business model of the startup? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Business-to-Consumer (B2C)
- Business-to-Business (B2B)
- Business-to-Business-to-Consumer (B2B2C)
- Business to Government (B2G)
- Outro: _____

15. What is the most important sector that the startup develops software for, or serves? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Professional, scientific, technical activities (software consultant, auditing, marketing, research, etc)
- Information & Communication
- Electricity & Oil/Gas supply
- Automotive (autonomous car, etc)
- Energy (green, sustainable energy, etc)
- Banking, Insurance & Finance
- Arts, creativity and recreation
- Healthcare & Social Work
- Agriculture, forestry and fishing
- Aerospace & Space
- Wholesale & Retail Trade
- Education
- Entertainment & Games
- Chemical
- Food & Beverage
- Construction
- Water supply; sewerage, waste management
- Transportation and storage
- Real estate
- Outro: _____

16. What is the state of the product/service created in the startup? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- A product prototype is developed and has not yet been released to the market.
- A product was released to the market and is actively developed further with customer input.
- The product is rather stable; the focus is on gaining a customer base.
- The product is stable, market size, share, and growth rate are established. The focus is set on launching new variations of the product.
- Outro: _____

Section 3: UX Methods and Practices

To answer the questions, consider how UX work is performed in the startup you are working for.

17. Does the startup you work for have UX-specific professionals who work with UX methodologies, techniques, or practices? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes, there is a team with at least 2 professionals dedicated entirely to UX work.
- Yes, there is a team with at least 2 professionals partially dedicated to UX work.
- Yes, there is a professional dedicated entirely to UX work.
- Yes, there is a professional partially dedicated to UX work.
- No, but the startup trains employees from other areas to carry out UX work.
- No, there's no-one doing UX work.
- I don't know.

18. Does the startup you work for use UX methodologies, techniques, or practices in product/service development? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Always
- Often
- Rarely
- Never
- I don't know

19. How many years have UX methodologies, techniques, or practices been introduced for in the startup? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 2 years
- 2 to 3 years
- More than 3 years
- Not Applicable

Section 4: UX issues found in startups

In the next sections, please answer the questions based on the 14 statements provided within framed boxes. These statements are based on UX issues identified from our early work and that we are aiming to find out how widely these issues are faced by startups.

Identifying real points of UX improvement

Complaints and suggestions from users can be linked to a range of issues. Not all user requests can be fulfilled. Some points are valuable, but others are not so much. Some issues are urgent, but others can be postponed (planning and prioritizing). Some tasks are actionable, but others may be hard to put into practice. In general, the issue is that it can be tricky to identify real points of UX improvement to be implemented in the startup.

20. Did you recognize this issue in the startup you work for? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes, this is an issue in the startup, we still have no solution.
- Yes, this issue exists in the startup but it is being resolved.
- Yes, this issue existed in the startup, but it has now been resolved.
- No, this issue has not yet been identified in the startup.
- Outro: _____

21. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Bringing together user information

User information is scattered around different touch-points and communication channels. In order to obtain insightful information about the user experience, the teams dealing with the product need to have broad access to this user information. However, the issue is how to bring together user information that is scattered across the startup.

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23. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Documenting demands coming from users

When users' demands are received, they need to be screened (sorted) and assigned to right professionals (qualified, responsible) to develop a solution. Afterward, the resolution process of these demands must be followed up (tracking). The issue is that demands coming from users need to be managed.

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- Outro: _____

25. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Identifying problems through metrics

User's data can be automatically collected to identify insights related to UX. However, using metrics is not a common practice. By using the right metrics, startups are able to prove that they are providing value to their customers and users. The issue is how to identify UX improvement opportunities using metrics.

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27. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Identifying UX insights from user data

Design decisions are often made based on the feelings and experiences of practitioners. Better decisions can be made based on real user data. These data can contain precious information to drive a good UX. However, there is a lot of user data that can be distributed across different sources and formats. The issue is how to identify meaningful UX information from user data.

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29. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Responding to users' demands

Most startups have limited resources, and often do not have enough human resources to deal with the great number of users' requests that they receive. They can have multiple channels of communication with their customers/users, and collect a lot of user feedback and requests daily. Many times, customers complain about recurring problems that require an urgent solution. The issue is how to respond to user demands timely.

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31. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Research and evaluation with real users

Understanding the impact of a product is needed to gain an understanding of end-users profiles, their needs, behaviors, goals, preferences, and pains from the beginning. However, when designing their products, many startups gather non-functional requirements from their customers rather than investigating the real needs of end-users of the product. The issue is how to get knowledge about the demand and acceptance of the product from real users.

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33. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Documentation of UX artifacts and decisions

Product design activities generate different types of artifacts such as flows, wireframes, prototypes, information about users and their needs, design decisions, and implementation details, among others. However, due to time-to-market pressure and the high pace of change the product undergoes, it becomes difficult to document UX deliverables in a structured way. The issue is how to properly keep UX artifacts and decisions documentation.

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35. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Promoting UX culture

Sometimes, the benefits of UX to the startup business not recognized by the startup team. However, a premise for successful UX work is the buy-in of all the company's professionals. UX principles and a user-centric mindset need to be part of the company's strategy. The issue is how to promote the UX culture at a startup.

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37. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Understanding the value of UX

Customer satisfaction is essential for business success. UX can help software startups to design experiences that satisfy customers. In consequence, positive experiences should help keep a user loyal to their products and services. Often, startups do not prioritize the UX process and do not understand how it can benefit them right away. The issue is how to show the value of UX.

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- Outro: _____

39. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Professional input on UX

The UX work consists of identifying target users, understanding their pains, behaviors, and preferences, and, consequently, allowing software professionals to define better design solutions to meet the real users' needs. As a result, UX work contributes to reaching customer satisfaction and building trust in the brand and product. The issue is how to have professional input on UX.

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41. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Understanding how to start doing UX

Startup teams from different areas often don't share the same product vision or know the limitations of the business. There are many uncertainties about the real users' needs and preferences. Teams do not have UX knowledge enough to introduce UX design practices in their process and the startup still does not have enough resources to hire an expert to input the UX work. The issue is how to start doing UX.

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43. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Improving communication between teams

To scale its business, a startup needs to hire more people with different expertise, including establishing a design (UI+UX) area that could not exist at first. At this stage, new employees are hired and communication problems often arise leading to a lack of alignment between teams. The issue is how to improve communication between teams.

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45. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

UX roles and jobs description

Startups need to hire employees to work in different areas including UX design to meet the growing demands for product enhancement and the creation of new features. When the team is small, professionals are often involved in various types of activities and the boundary between roles can be unclear. During the onboarding process, UX professionals may take time to understand where and how they will apply their skills. The problem is how to make the UX roles clearer.

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- Outro: _____

47. Please elaborate on your response, e.g. how has it been resolved or further details of the issue in your startup?

Section 5: Final remarks

Thank you for completing our survey!

48. We intend to conduct other steps in this study. Please inform your email address below if you want to be contacted to participate in a feedback interview.

49. Do you want to receive the outputs of this survey? If so, please inform your email address.

Oh, sorry!

50. This survey is intended for professionals working in software startups. However, let us know if you would like to receive the results of this survey by entering your email address below. If you can, please share this survey with other people who work in startups. We appreciate your attention!

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